

Asymmetric Reduction of α -Keto-acids and their Derivatives by Alkoxyaluminium Dichlorides

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It has previously been shown by us¹ that isobornoxyaluminium dichloride², prepared from 'mixed hydride' and (-)isborneol reduces a variety of aliphatic and aromatic ketones with high asymmetric induction*. The method provides a simple and useful means for preparing partially active alcohols from dissymmetrical ketones. The isolation of the alcohols in pure state, however, is often very tedious. This difficulty may be circumvented by the use of keto-acids, esters, or nitriles in place of simple ketones, which after reduction can readily be hydrolysed and isolated through sodium salt. Phenylglyoxylic acid and the corresponding ester and nitrile seem to be suitable system for such study in view of their ready availability and known high optical rotation of the resultant hydroxyacid. These have now been reduced by alkoxyaluminium dichlorides derived from (-)isborneol, (-)borneol, and (-)menthol, all of known configuration.

The reduction was carried out under three slightly different conditions which vary only in the order of addition of the reagent components. In the normal procedure, previously adopted¹ (method A), the 'mixed hydride' was prepared first and to it the desired active alcohol introduced in equimolecular proportion. In method B, lithium aluminium tetra-alkoxide was formed by addition of alcohol (or ketone like d-camphor) to lithium aluminium hydride and then an ethereal solution of aluminium chloride slowly introduced. The ketonic compounds were added to the reagent thus formed. The results were almost identical in both the cases as one would expect. In the third variation (method C), the ketone was added to lithium aluminium tetra-alkoxide and a solution of aluminium chloride introduced later to effect the reduction. As seen from the Table I, the result differed considerably from those of methods A and B. Phenylglyoxylic acid was previously reduced asymmetrically by Vavon *et al.*⁴ by optically active alkoxy-magnesium-bromide derivatives. Their results are also incorporated in the table under the heading D, for sake of comparison.

*After the publication of our results¹, our attention was drawn to a recent communication by Horeau³ dealing with similar reagent, which prompted us to report the present data.

1. D. Nasipuri and G. Sarker, this *Journal*, 1967, 44, 165.
2. E. L. Eliel and D. Nasipuri, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1965, 30, 3809.
3. D. Mea-Jacheet and A. Horeau, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Fr.* 1966, 3040.
4. G. Vavon and A. Antonini, *Compt. rend.* 1951, 232, 1120.

TABLE I

Entry No.	Reagent Derived from:	Method	Mandelic Acid from:					
			1		2		3	
			PhCOCO ₂ H		PhCOCO ₂ Et		PhCOCN	
[α] _D ^b , Optical yield ^a		[α] _D , Optical yield		[α] _D , Optical yield				
1.	(-) Isoborneol ^a	A	+11.9,	7.44	+28.0,	17.15	+3.6,	2.25
		B	+13.0,	8.13	+23.0,	14.4	+6.3,	3.9
		C	-8.0,	5.0	-31.5,	19.7	0.0,	0.0
		D	+24.0,	15.0	—	—	—	—
2.	(-) Borneol	A	-83.0,	51.9	+14.3,	8.9	-14.6,	9.1
		B	-77.0,	48.1	—	—	—	—
		C	-91.8,	57.4	—	—	—	—
		D	No reduction					
3.	(-) Menthol	A	-1.55 ^d ,	1.0	-6.15 ^d ,	3.85	—	—
		D	+54.0,	33.0	—	—	—	—

^aA mixture of (-) isoborneol (90%) and (+) borneol (10%) obtained by reduction of d-camphor was used.

^bRotations (in degree) were taken at 20° in ethanol solution (c, 2-10). ^cCalculated as 100X[α]_D observed/[α]_D maximum; the maximum rotation of mandelic acid was taken as 160.0.

^dThe reduction was incomplete.

The mandelic acid in majority of cases was dextrorotatory having absolute S configuration, consistent with previously discussed¹ preferred transition state in which Ph group (larger than CO₂H) and the more heavily substituted α -carbon atoms (C₁ in case of borneol and isoborneol, C₂ in menthol) of the cyclic alcohols are on the opposite sides of the (quasi six-membered ring. According to this argument, (-)borneol and (-)menthol should also produce (+)mandelic acid as the preponderant enantiomer. However in practice, reduction of phenylglyoxylic acid with (-)borneol complex furnished (-)mandelic acid with highest asymmetric induction (37%) in this series. There were also a few other cases of exception (entries 1C column 1, 2A column 3, and 3A columns 1 & 2). Obviously in these cases, CO₂H (and to some extent CN) behaves as a larger group than phenyl. The only rationale we can suggest at the moment for this apparent discrepancy is that with slow-reacting reagent like borneol and menthol derivatives, the carboxylic (and possibly nitrile) group forms some sort of chloroaluminium complex by interaction with aluminium chloride or the reagent itself, before the ketonic function is reduced. Such groups, perhaps further modified by solvation, become effectively larger than phenyl and the induction is reversed. Incidentally, the tendency of the carboxylic and nitrile groups to form complex with aluminium chloride may be responsible for relatively low asymmetric induction in the present instances.

In contrast to the results of Vavon *et al.*, the reduction of the ketones with isoborneol and borneol complexes was complete but that with menthol incomplete. This is in agreement with our previous finding that isoborneol and borneol complexes are good reducing

agents while cyclohexanol complex is a poor one, with the equilibrium lying well towards cyclohexanol side⁷. Isobornyloxyaluminium dichloride, however fails to reduce p-anisyl methyl ketone, β -methylnaphthone, and α -tetralone. The dichloroaluminium derivatives of the alcohols corresponding to these ketones would therefore be very good hydride transferring reagents. This was found to be true for p-anisylmethylcarbinol and methyl-naphthylcarbinol which are good reducing agents. Details of these experiments will be published later.

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